

Textbook: Focus on Students' National Identity

Textbooks on theoretical disciplines for "generation z" students

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Abstract

The paper deals with the actual problem of textbooks and teaching aids' creation while taking into account the social, psychophysical and psycholinguistic features of modern students of language specialties, who, along with practical language courses, receive theoretical training. A new generation of students, often called the generation of "zoomers", as well as the introduction of the online learning based on the educational platforms Zoom and Teams, revealed the urgent need to modernize the learning process, introduce new forms of work, as well as to create textbooks and teaching aids of a new type. The work draws attention to the trainees' characteristics, which distinguish the current generation from their predecessors, for example, pragmatism, multi-activity, self-confidence, digitalization, and a number of others. Based on the experience of teaching and analyzing the research of Russian linguists, linguo-didacts, and textbook authors, the paper suggests the possibility of creating textbooks and manuals that overcome the students' shortcomings and use their typical traits to improve the quality of education. The result of the study was the development of criteria for the formation of a textbook on theoretical disciplines. These criteria describe both approaches to the material organization in the textbook and the revision of the educational process organization, in particular, the refusal from the standard model of "teacher-student", which allows the student to become a "co-creator" of a practical or a theoretical lesson. A new type of textbook becomes a multi-modal complex that takes into account not only the modern students' specifics, but also has technical characteristics that meet the ideas of the latest technologies. The practical significance of the study results is the possibility of creating a pilot project of a textbook on theoretical disciplines for undergraduate students, structured in accordance with the criteria described in this research paper.

Keywords distance learning, a new type of a textbook, Z generation.

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Introduction

The urgency of the problem, which consists in the need to create a new type of textbook, is seen in the realities of the present period. Both professional teachers, people of other professions and even parents cannot pass by the changes that occur with modern youth, in particular, with 16-25 years old people. In accordance with the tradition established in American sociology, they are a generation of "zoomers" (or 'digital aborigines') who strive for inclusivity and individuality, for maximum openness and inclusion in the electronic environment, at the same time. They are not just focused on digital as an information medium, they also broadcast their life scenarios simultaneously on several platforms, thereby forming a new philosophy of moving away from the "beautiful picture and the ideal world" to a world, free from stereotypes, and a single role model.

In addition to the change of students' generations, one can also observe new trends in the educational environment. The appearance of new educational programs on various alternative platforms, which are very attractive for "zoomers", can not but predict the future of classical university education. They are those learning models that may be of interest not only for today's students, but also for future generations. The emergence of new models, such as microlearning, or the innovative platform "Young Professionals (Worldskills Russia)", which forms new standards of modern working professions and revises the examination system in colleges and universities, may indicate not only the crisis of the classical teaching system, but also the rapidly growing demand for alternative ways of mastering professions that are in demand today, as well as having prospects for the coming decades. The platform is able to identify deficiencies in the students' knowledge, offers alternative and independent forms of knowledge control, and creates FutureSkills, a new cluster of competencies that may be required by specialists in the near future, which will avoid wasting time on obtaining unnecessary knowledge and the lack of demand for young personnel in the labor market.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of this study is to qualitatively rethink the role and quality of textbooks in theoretical disciplines for the "z" generation, which should lead to the emergence of a new type of textbook model. In the course of developing such a model, it is necessary to take the realities of modern life as a basis, including the introduction of new technologies and remote work into the educational process. Moreover, it is important to get involved in the outline of scientific discourse, which provides a qualitative, well-

founded analysis of modern pedagogical and linguo-didactic approaches that allow us to solve this problem.

Literature review

The classical education system, which was considered a constant, is beginning to change rapidly in the 21st century, "reacting to changes in the surrounding environment and demonstrating readiness for numerous, sometimes unforeseen, changes of evolutionary and revolutionary nature" (Tareva, 2015). Rethinking the role of education involves its focus not only on the knowledge acquisition, but also on the "explication of goals and values in the field of teaching and upbringing" (this, in relation to teaching a foreign language, is described by Tareva, 2015; Tareva, Galskova, 2013).

The emergence of new educational practices, to which both microlearning and Worldskills Russia belong, makes the educational system more practice-oriented, emphasize the non-standard nature of its modern, innovative nature by moving away from the traditional generally accepted categories of "educational technologies", "educational models", "educational strategies" (Tareva, 2015). One of the signs of innovative educational practices, noted by E. G. Tareva, is their "unconventionality", "absence of any system", resulting from the specific situation in which this practice originated. As a rule, it appears in a situation when a teacher or teaching staff is forced, due to certain circumstances, to use new forms of work that can solve the tasks set. However, the very process of mastering these innovative methods inevitably leads to the idea that the new practice is moving from the category "useful for me personally" to the category "useful for everyone" (Tareva, 2015). This situation is fully applicable to the educational process, introduced in 2020 in the form of distance learning, when universities' teaching teams all over the world (Fleuß, 2020; Lörz, 2020; Lörz, 2021) were not only urgently mastering Zoom and Microsoft Teams systems, but also solved the problems of rethinking the educational process. To solve all the tasks assigned to the teacher, it was necessary not only to master the technique, not only to fundamentally revise the material presentation, but also to get engaged in the analysis of all the educational process components, including textbooks on theoretical disciplines and their role in the new circumstances (Traus, 2020).

The introduction of new platforms into the educational process, digitalization of the whole life, not just of the learning process, can lead to the idea of a complete rejection of classical teaching methods and immersion in absolute digitalization (Busen, 2020). However, "the optimism of many digitalization apologists still causes some concern. Modern civilization, based on the technologies of mass reading and writing, is text-based. Digitalization, however, leads to the rejection of the need to read, memorize and write texts. In fact, there is a return to the audiovisual perception of the world, characteristic of ancient

people. Accordingly, there are risks of a sharp drop in the level of literacy, including the loss of many cognitive abilities several generations later" (Fomin-Nilov, 2019). Therefore, an innovative textbook must contain texts included in the digital environment, in a neural network, and this imposes new requirements on all educational process participants.

A new type of textbook should possess the following features: authenticity, communication, modularity, multi-level orientation, emphasizing the student's personality, preparation for educational autonomy through self-planning, self-checking and self-control, focus on solving problems of training, education and development (Tareva, Tarev, 2014; cit. by: Yastrebova, 2019). Such a textbook can help to optimally achieve the ultimate goal of training – to contribute to the formation of a professional personality of a of the 21st century. Of course, this kind of textbook is designed for innovative teaching staff, as well as for students with developed critical thinking and a humanistic position.

Case-methods focused primarily on practice-oriented technologies can and should become a component of the future textbook. A case is a description of a situation that includes a problem and a task to find a solution to this problem. "At the same time, the problem itself is not explicated, its identification requires efforts on the part of students. The proposed situation is usually described from the point of view of the person who will make the decision based on the findings. Accordingly, an incorrectly defined problem leads to an incorrect algorithm of actions and making incorrect decisions" (Tareva, 2018). The attractiveness of the cases included in the textbook material lies in their focus on the student's future professional activity, on the reproduction of situations that they will face, as well as in the fact that they can increase the students' motivation.

Recently, the scientific directions that implement the ideas of cognitive learning have attracted great attention of the pedagogical community. We are talking about cognitive visualization of didactic objects and processes, perception poly-modality and information recoding, visual schematization and logical structuring of the learning content (Bershadskaya, 2011; Bershadskiy, 2011; Novak, 2008).

These can be educational technologies based on quantized educational texts, educational technologies based on the frame representation of knowledge, modeling of didactic objects based on cognitive visualization. The material can be presented in the form of hypertext — the technology of "presenting information based on associative links and semantic coherence of its elements, presented in the text explicitly in the form of cross-references". All these cognitive technologies can be used both in the creation of a new type of textbook, and included in the educational process, where the textbook will be a tool for obtaining new knowledge, feedback from the student, etc.

Methodology

Classical university education cannot remain a passive observer of the processes taking place in the country and the world. The pedagogical community should get involved in the creation of new learning models, create new didactic materials that meet the society needs. The introduction of the Master's program "Foreign languages in the sphere of business intercultural communication" at Moscow City Pedagogical University, aimed at future specialists in the field of mass communications who are able to ensure, evaluate and predict the impact of official texts, PR texts, as well as social networks on domestic and foreign audiences, raised the question of working methods, the need to introduce new tools, innovative means of intermediate control, allowing students to be involved in the educational process, to diversify the educational material, as well as to provide undergraduates with the competencies necessary for future specialists.

The distance-learning regime in Russian universities, introduced due to the coronavirus situation, also significantly affected the awareness of the urgency of involve teaching staff into the study of the problem. A thorough analysis of all forms of work was required: lectures, seminars, as well as students' independent work.

The researchers were guided by general professional competencies that should be formed as a result of mastering the "Marketing Linguistics" module, the part of the educational program "Foreign languages in the sphere of business intercultural communication" in the training direction 45.04.02 "Linguistics". As part of our research, we paid special attention to the process of forming certain competencies, since this process has become quite dynamic precisely in the conditions of using the Microsoft Teams educational platform. We are talking about the formation of competencies that were the key to effective cooperation between teachers and students, a creative atmosphere, and the involvement of the maximum number of Internet resources in the educational process. First of all, the following competencies should be mentioned:

- the ability to structure and integrate knowledge from various fields of professional activity and to be able to creatively use and develop this knowledge while solving professional problems;
- the ability to use theoretical foundations and practical methods of solving professional problems in cognitive and research activities;
- possession of systematic knowledge in the field of team psychology and company management skills;

- analysis and processing the research material and conducting empirical studies of problem situations and dissonances in the field of intercultural communication;
- the ability to assess the quality of research in this subject area, to correlate new information with existing one, to logically and consistently present the results of one's own research.

Researchers, primarily sociologists, have been raising the question of distinguishing a group of people by their generation for about half a century, although it was also mentioned earlier, in art and philosophy. Today, the interest has clearly increased and spread to other areas of knowledge: psychology, linguistics (cf. the concept of generational linguistics by Borisova, 2019; Borisova, 2020), political science. Different methods were used to identify a particular generation, including historical landmarks, changes in the value system, and psychophysiological characteristics.

The rapid change in the stereotypes of young people's behavior and ideas forced, first, writers, and then sociologists and other scientists to single out the generations of the late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries, almost every decade.

In these studies, we are primarily interested in the generation corresponding to the age of university students in their cognitive and psychophysiological aspects, since this is related to learning abilities. These features are quite noticeable for teachers who are attentive to their students' mental features. There are usually qualities that are regarded as negative: mosaic perception (lack of inclination or even inability to generalize), pragmatic motivation to study (little interest in scientific deepening) vs the desire for independence, which can result in a refusal to assimilate the material presented in an axiomatic form, but, at the same time, a tendency to make independent conclusions). Finally, they demonstrate obvious multimodality, i.e. the displacement of verbal perception of information by visual perception.

It is easy to see that most of these qualities really contradict the requirements of a deep understanding of the subject and the formation of a complete picture of the specialist's world. And it is in the course of studying theoretical subjects that these shortcomings (or, to put it mildly, the perception peculiarities) must be overcome. Yet, on the other hand, these features make it possible to develop such training methods, when overcoming would not be the result of breaking behavioral attitudes, but using the reverse side of these properties, which make it possible to achieve goals based on this specifics.

Observations of the students' work in the Microsoft Teams system, their speed of information processing, the form of completed tasks and projects' presentation, the motivational component analysis allowed us, on the one hand, to identify the features characteristic of the "zoomers" generation, on the other hand, to note

the advantages of this type of training, which can be transferred to the educational environment, including offline mode. A new type of textbook can be the most effective tool for bringing together the technological features of the "new" learning process and the most modern linguo-didactic approaches.

Mosaic perception or "clip thinking" is one of the characteristics attributed to the "zoomers" generation. As a rule, this type of perception is connoted negatively. Scientists say that the "clip thinking" generation is not able to penetrate deeply into the material, is not able to analyze, and perceives the world around them and scientific information superficially. However, we tend to think that the modern man is in an information-saturated world. A person living in the 21st century can meet more people in a day than his ancestor in a lifetime. At the same time, he/she receives information from different sources; the received quanta of information relate to different topics and are included in a wide variety of discourses. In our opinion, "clip thinking" is both a defensive reaction to the uncontrolled flow of information, and a certain mechanism that helps to master this information. The apparent disadvantage can be turned into an advantage if the educational process combines the same diverse sources of information, different forms of material presentation.

A new type of textbook could be a link in this process. For example, in the Master's program "Foreign languages in the sphere of modern intercultural communication", within the discipline "Advertisement language specifics", it is necessary to reflect the specifics of film, Internet, video and television advertising, the advantages of screen advertising over other types of advertising, new opportunities for computer graphics and their use in creating video ads. As experience has shown, the lecture form of the material presentation, even accompanied by a presentation, will not give the desired effect. To achieve the result, it is necessary to switch the students' attention to video clips of interviews or experts' lectures: domestic and foreign linguists. Then, as an illustrative material, one, together with the students, needs to analyze the advertising products themselves on various portals, simultaneously returning to both the lecturer's explanations and the textbook material. When doing homework, students themselves are the creators of advertising products, and the success of doing the task is possible only when the student uses all the above-mentioned sources of information. In this case, the student may be informed, for example, that he needs to watch the material of "Cannes Lions" commercials festival, which is quite consistent with the features of "clip thinking" and which can become a kind of bonus with this form of training.

The lesson scenario described above leads to the solution of one of the most important tasks the teacher faces: motivation boost. In our opinion, the student who is included in the new lesson scenario, different from the template, becomes its co-creator. Therefore, we are moving away from the standard teacher-student role distribution, which significantly affects motivation. However, the most important lever that can

change the student's attitude to the subject, the material, the course of the lesson is the understanding that he/she receives not only knowledge, but also real tools that can help him in his future (or already existing) profession. One doesn't need to study the theory of the means of promoting the introduction of information into consciousness, but to create one's own texts in the Instagram account created as part of the Master's program, where one needs to use emotionally colored vocabulary, to use empathy as a tool to attract subscribers to the discussion, etc.

The use of a new type of textbook, the use of technical means, access to the Internet during classes lead to the fact that the student becomes a co-author of the lesson scenario. Performing a particular task, the student must mobilize not only all his/her theoretical knowledge, must not only use all the formed competencies, but also apply all his/her creativity to get a unique product. Within the framework of the Master's program "Foreign languages in the sphere of modern intercultural communication", "Advertisement language specifics" disciplines and "Linguistic foundations of text analysis and creation", the final classes were devoted to demonstration and analysis of the students' own scenarios of advertisement and music videos, the selection of musical accompaniment, discussion of the target audience, etc. It is obvious that creativity in itself can not be either an evaluation criterion or an indicator of the material being mastered. Yet without it, it is impossible to implement the task, and therefore, it is impossible to approach the specified standards of professions related to advertising, PR, etc.

Results

Now, after listing the main psychological characteristics of young people born in 1995-2005, belonging to the "z-generation", it is possible to outline the characteristics that a textbook designed for them should have, and, importantly, in theoretical disciplines.

First of all, we emphasize that the textbook should be based on a fairly compact, but at the same time logical, interconnected backbone of information. These should be the main scientific statements presented in conjunction with the justification in the field of fundamental sciences, i.e. based on original scientific works, and received evidence in the course of specific, applied research. This position should overcome the mosaic picture of the world, which is characteristic of most students. In addition, it should create a foundation for obtaining knowledge that is more detailed. Moreover, based on this foundation, the student should feel the non-randomness of those theses and provisions that he/she will learn in the course of acquaintance with a particular discipline.

In particular, for a sociolinguistics textbook, it is important to include such postulates as "language is a system where everything is interconnected", "language is a means of communication, and therefore it lives

in the communicating society", "people speak the way the communities where they are included speak" into the text from the very beginning, and then trace through all the themes. At the same time, all the provisions should be illustrated immediately after the introduction, as well as in the course of studying the material, including when students work independently. For example,

"Get to know the creolized language of Runorsk. Note the sources and terms of using the roots of Russian and Norwegian origin. Which of them confirm the statement about the connection between the language and the society in which it functions. Does the existence of this creolized language contradict the postulate "Language is a system in which everything is interconnected"?"

The textbook must necessarily set the motivation for mastering the material, which is usually difficult for those who are not used to or do not like to think logically, to comprehend the essence of things. In the future, the motivation may be an interest in the fact, the joy of understanding new things, from independently made conclusions. Yet most students need to be led to this for a long time. You need to start by linking theoretical knowledge to practical needs. For example, the provision on the language consistency creates the prerequisites for ensuring the memorization of individual facts presented as a system during teaching. In the future, tasks for independent identification of language features based according to specially selected data ("linguistic tasks"), and then on independently collected material, can awaken students' curiosity, joy from the solved problem, which creates prerequisites for the emergence of other types of motivation.

The solution of the motivation problem, as it was shown, directly leads to such a textbook tasks' property as emphasis on creativity. Actually, this feature has been widely used in school textbooks since the 80-ies. The game-centered specifics of the child and adolescent psyche is used. However, the same component is present in the adults' value system. In addition, success in completing a task by an adult includes more complex motivational moments: increasing self-esteem in obtaining a profession in the future, the possibility of including such tasks in professional activities, i.e. entering the research path.

The reform of the textbook also involves more intensive work with information, changing the speed of its processing. Therefore, the creators of the textbook of the future need to turn to the technologies of cognitive visualization of information. This can be info-graphics, mental maps, scribing, as well as a navigation device that allows you to easily find the necessary information, to combine the material of various paragraphs and chapters of the textbook to complete the task, and record the material covered. The cognitive technologies used in the textbook allow us to structure information obtained from different sources, as well as to create one's own e-portfolio that records personal achievements.

Multimodality is one of the principles of building a new type of a textbook. The main question that the authors should ask themselves is how the information pieces transmitted from different sources will be integrated with each other. It is assumed that visual, acoustic, verbal and non-verbal data can both be harmoniously interwoven into the outline of the textbook, and generate contradictions between different components of the discourse. To optimize a textbook that has a multi-modality, it is necessary to use data from multi-modal linguistics, a new direction of linguistic knowledge that is developing in the 21st century.

The introduction of distance learning in 2020 once again showed the need for a new format of the textbook, assuming its electronic form, the ability to "synchronize" the textbook with the platform on which classes with students are held, for example, Microsoft Teams, as well as the inclusion of all those resources that are traditionally used by the "zoomers" generation in extracurricular time. At the same time, students' attention is redirected to solving educational tasks that become fascinating because they coincide with the traditional scenarios describing this generation. During classes, they do not need to part with their smartphone, it is no longer a hindrance in learning: it is a tool for obtaining, consolidating new knowledge, as well as for completing tasks. The use of streaming, the Instagram network, and viewing Youtube channels can not only diversify the educational process, enrich the material being mastered with new and relevant data, but also significantly increase the students' motivation. The features embedded in the upgraded new-generation textbook, which involve the use of such training scenarios, are taking the learning process to a new level.

Discussions

These requirements for the content of the textbook make us think about the forms of information presentation. And here it's the right time to remember that for Z generation (and for older generations, too), the paper form of the book is almost out of use. Even fiction and entertainment literature is mostly read on electronic media: special readers, on a computer or a tablet, and most often on a smartphone.

These features are taken into account by modern publishing houses that provide access to educational, scientific and other texts through Internet resources. A number of educational publishers organize media support: reference materials, video comments to the textbooks they published. In particular, this applies to "Youwrite" publishing house. In any case, textbooks, like other texts, are often sold in electronic form, even if there is a paper version.

The authors of this paper have some experience in creating didactic materials in a digital form. So, E. G. Borisova back in 2010 made a small textbook on Internet journalism (then this meant working with

websites, to a lesser extent with blogs). The tutorial was made on a platform designed for maintaining websites based on Javascript. Despite the modesty of the design: a small volume, no illustrations or even multimedia files, the textbook allowed, using hyperlinks, to organize different trajectories of movement through the material, depending on the students' interests and capabilities. The textbook was used in classes in "advertising and public relations" specialty. After a few years, it became obsolete due to rapid changes in the field of Internet communications, although the form principally allowed for regular updates and changes to the submitted information.

Conclusion

These days, as number of publishers' experience shows that online textbooks have much wider possibilities. Therefore, we consider it reasonable to focus on the digital form of material presentation in such textbooks, rather than on paper, when developing the main provisions and concepts of a modern textbook on theoretical disciplines.

This corresponds to the general theoretical guidelines concerning the use of psychological, psychophysiological and ethical characteristics of modern youth, which we discussed in Section 2 and which we used as the basis for developing the concept of the textbook. In particular, thanks to this form, the student gets access to educational information at a convenient time and in an acceptable form (for example, a voiced one). The issue of illustrations to the main provisions, including audio and video fragments, is being resolved. It is more convenient to go to reference sources, to search, to the latest scientific discoveries recommended during the course. The methods of feedback, verification, etc. also get somewhat easier.

At the same time, digital textbooks have enough opportunities to preserve the most important, from our point of view, attitudes to the integrity of scientific representation, the validity of conclusions: these questions can be included in tasks, be presented on the margins with hyperlinks.

Finally, the flexibility of the digital representation of knowledge should be taken into account. New information, new research results in the relevant field of knowledge can be included in such a textbook quite quickly, even taking into account the necessary formalities that accompany any publication, including electronic.

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